

“YONIGADHEEKARANA EFFICACY OF LODHRA-KATUTUMBI TAILA AND PALASHADI TAILA – YONIPICHUDHARANA IN YONIBHRAMSHA (PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE): A RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIAL”

Dr. Apoorva Ashok Shetty*¹, Dr. Sumarani Rajesh²

¹*Third Year PG Scholar, Department of PG Studies in Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodubidire 574 227, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, India.

²Professor & HOD, Department of PG Studies in Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodubidire 574 227, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, India.

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***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Apoorva Ashok Shetty

Third Year PG Scholar, Department of PG Studies in Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodubidire 574 227, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Yonibhramsha refers to the displacement or prolapse of female reproductive organs from their normal anatomical position. Though not described as a distinct entity in classical Ayurvedic texts, concept aligns with *Vatiki Yonivyapat* as mentioned by *Acharya Vagbhata*. Clinically, it resembles Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP), common gynecological condition, especially among parous women. Ayurvedic conditions related to POP include *Vatiki*, *Andini*, *Phalini*, *Prasramsini*, and *Mahayoni Yonivyapat*. The term “*Yonigadheekarana*” combines “*Yoni*” (female reproductive system) and “*Gadheekarana*” (strengthening) and is referenced in some classical texts for postnatal care and local treatments. POP arises due to weakened pelvic support structures and *Yonigadheekarana* aims to restore structural integrity. Symptomatic POP affects 3–6% of women, while anatomical prolapse may occur in up to 50%. Conservative, surgical and mesh-based interventions are associated with complications. Hence the present study was undertaken to evaluate efficacy of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila* and

Palashadi Taila – Yonipichudharana for *Yonigadheekarana* in *Yonibhramsha* (POP). The study was randomised controlled clinical study with pre and post-test evaluation with total 40 patients of *Yonibhramsha* divided into 2 groups of 20 each. Subjects in Group A were administered with *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and Group B were administered *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana*. The procedure was done for 14 days after cessation of menstruation for 2 consecutive months. In menopausal patients, the procedure was started on the day of enrolment. The subjects were observed and assessment was done using statistical tests. The test of significance showed that the efficacy of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* for *Yonigadheekarana* in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse) is statistically significant within the groups and both *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* are equally effective for *Yonigadheekarana* in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse).

KEYWORDS: *Yonibhramsha; Yonipichudharana; Yonigadheekarana; Pelvic Organ Prolapse; Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila; Palashadi Taila.*

INTRODUCTION

Yonibhramsha is a clinical condition in which displacement of female genital organs (uterus and vaginal walls) occur from its normal position. Even though *Yonibhramsha* is not explained as a single entity, the term *Bhramsha* is mentioned in *Vatiki Yonivyapat* by *Acharya Vagbhata*. The condition of *Yonibhramsha* is having close resemblance with Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) based on its signs and symptoms like feeling of mass in vagina, low back ache, dyspareunia, urinary and bowel symptoms and white or blood-stained discharge per vagina. POP is one of the common clinical conditions met in day-to-day gynecological practice especially among the parous women. *Yonivyapat* which are resembles POP are *Vatiki Yonivyapat, Andini Yonivyapat, Phalini Yonivyapat, Prasramsini Yonivyapat, Mahayoni / Mahati Yonivyapat*.

The word “*Yonigadheekarana*” comprises of two words, *yon* and *gadheekarana*. *Yon* means female reproductive system which includes vagina, uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries and related other accessory pelvic structures. Specific meaning is to be taken according to different context. The term *gadheekarana* refers to the process of strengthening or consolidating. The concept of “*Yonigadheekarana*” can be found in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Strirogadhikara. Prasavoparanta Yonigadheekarana*^[1] can be found in *Bhava Prakasha Chikitsa Sthana*, and *Vangasena* mentions *Sthanika Chikitsa* for *Bhaga Gadhatva*.^[2] Integrity

of support structures of pelvic organs is fundamental to pelvic organ stability. The Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) occurs due to weakness of the structures supporting the organs in position,^[3] where *Yonigadheekarana* can be utilized for strengthening supporting structures.

It is difficult to assess the true prevalence of POP. However, symptomatic POP has a prevalence of 3% to 6%, and anatomic prolapse occurs in up to 50% of women.^[4] The prevalence of prolapse of the vaginal cuff following hysterectomy was reported to be as high as 6%-12%.^[5] The incidence of POP is highly associated with increased age. It is projected to increase by 46%, by 2050.^[6]

The conservative treatment of POP with Pessary, surgical management and pelvic repair with mesh are associated with complications.^{[6][7]} Hence, *Yonipichudharana* one among the *Sthanika Chikitsa* mentioned for *Yonirogas* in which medicines are administered intravaginally, can overcome the limitations of conservative and surgical management. As vaginal wall and adjacent tissues are highly vascular and facilitates absorption of drugs through vaginal mucosa and surrounding tissues, an attempt was made to study the *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* so that need for surgical management could be avoided.

AIM OF THE STUDY

To compare the *Yonigadheekarana* efficacy of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* with *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the *Yonigadheekarana* effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse).
- To compare the *Yonigadheekarana* effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* with *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse) with reference of POP-Q Scale and accessory symptoms of pelvic pain, lower abdominal symptoms, and urinary symptoms if any.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no statistically significant effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha*.

H₁: There is statistically more significant effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* than *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha*.

H₂: There is statistically more significant effect of *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* than *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha*.

H₃: There is no statistically significant difference in effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha*.

METHODOLOGY

This clinical study was carried out on 40 patients where they were randomly selected at Alva's Ayurveda OPD of Prasuti Tantra & Stree Roga and other referral sources. The preparation of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila* and *Palashadi Taila* was done according to classical references.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

A minimum of 40 patients of *Yonibhramsha* fulfilling the diagnostic and inclusion criteria in the age group of 30-70 years irrespective of religion, occupation, socio-economic status, educational status were selected for the study.

STUDY DESIGN

Randomised controlled clinical study with pre and post-test evaluation.

Sample size – Minimum of 40 subjects diagnosed with *Yonibhramsha*, fulfilling the inclusion criteria.

Grouping – 40 subjects were randomly divided through computer generated random sequence table, into two groups - Group A and Group B of 20 each.

Sampling method - Computer generated random sequence table.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Subjects with symptom of **feeling of mass per vaginum**

With or without,

- Backache or dragging pain in the pelvis
- Dyspareunia
- Urinary symptoms like incomplete evacuation, urgency and frequency of micturition, painful micturition, stress incontinence, difficulty in passing urine and urinary retention.
- Bowel symptoms like incomplete evacuation of faeces, difficulty in passing stools and faecal incontinence.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Subjects diagnosed with *Yonibhramsha* by POP-Q Scale
- Subjects fulfilling diagnostic criteria
- Married women of age group: 30-70 years
- Parous women.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Known case of genital, bladder and rectal organ malignancies
- Any trauma leading to POP
- Infectious disorders of genital tract
- Congenital anomalies leading to POP
- Pregnant woman
- Prolapse with fibroid uterus, ovarian or vaginal cyst
- Infectious diseases like HIV, VDRL, HBsAg
- Any systemic illness like hypertension, diabetes, tuberculosis and chronic cough
- Subjects with chronic constipation
- Parity ≥ 4
- Procidentia
- Subjects with irregular menstrual bleeding.

INTERVENTION

- Group A subjects were administered with *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* for 14 days for 2 consecutive months.
- Group B subjects were administered with *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* for 14 days for 2 consecutive months.

ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION

- Intravaginal route.

DURATION OF TREATMENT

- The procedure was done for 14 days after cessation of menstruation for 2 consecutive months.
- In menopausal patients, the procedure was started on the day of enrolment.

OBSERVATION PERIOD

On 1st, 7th and 14th day of treatment for 2 consecutive months.

FOLLOW UP PERIOD

On 21st day following treatment.

ASSESSMENT

The assessment was done BT (Before Treatment - 1st day of 1st month), AT1 (After Treatment 1 – 14th day of 1st month), AT2 (After Treatment 2 – 14th day of 2nd month) and FU (Follow Up – on 21st day following treatment). The effect of treatment was assessed by RM ANOVA on rank test if test for normality failed and Paired t test if test for normality passed for within the group comparison and Mann-Whitney test for between the group comparison.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA**SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS**

- Feeling of mass per vaginum
- Low back ache
- Frequency of micturition
- Stress Urinary Incontinence
- Difficulty in emptying bladder
- Straining during defecation.

OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

- POP-Q Scale for staging degree of prolapse
- Modified Oxford Grading System to evaluate the strength of pelvic floor muscles
- The PERFECT Scheme for pelvic floor muscle assessment.

SCORING OF SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

Table no. 1 -Scoring for feeling of mass per vaginum.

Criteria	Score
None	0
Mild (vague awareness, no effect on activities)	1
Moderate (clear sensation, sometimes interferes)	2
Severe (constant/obvious, limits activities)	3

Chart no. 1 – VAS Scale

Table no. 2 -Scoring for Low Back Ache.

VAS Scale	Criteria	Score
0	No pain	0
1-3	Mild	1
4-6	Moderate	2
≥ 7	Severe	3

Table no. 3 -Scoring for Frequency of micturition.

Criteria	Score
Normal (≤ 7 times/day, no bother)	0
Mild (8-10 times/day or slightly increased)	1
Moderate (11-13 times/day or wakes once at night)	2
Severe (≥ 14 times/day or ≥ 2 nocturia episodes)	3

Table no. 4 -Scoring for Stress Urinary Incontinence.

Criteria	Score
No Incontinence	0
Incontinence on cough or sneeze	1
Incontinence with mild exercise	2
Incontinence even with change of posture	3

Table no. 5 -Scoring for Difficulty in emptying bladder.

Criteria	Score
None (passes urine normally, no hesitancy or straining)	0
Mild (occasional hesitancy / slow stream, but no need to strain, no residual sensation)	1
Moderate (frequent hesitancy or intermittent stream, sometimes needs to strain or reposition)	2
Severe (requires regular straining / manual reduction of prolapse to void)	3

Table no. 6 -Scoring for Straining during defecation.

Criteria	Score
No effort – stool passes easily	0
Mild effort – slight push, not uncomfortable	1
Moderate effort – need to lean forward / brace abdominal wall	2
Severe effort – prolonged straining (>5 min) or feeling of incomplete evacuation	3

SCORING FOR OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

Table no. 7 -Scoring for stage of prolapse as assessed by POP Q Scale.

Stage	Criteria
0	No prolapse, points Aa, Ba, Ap & Bp are all at -3cm and C or D is between -TVL & -(TVL-2) cm
1	Most distal portion of the prolapse is >1cm above the level of hymen
2	Most distal portion of the prolapse \leq 1cm proximal or distal to the plane of the hymen
3	Most distal portion of the prolapse is >1cm below the level of the hymen but protrudes no farther than 2 cm less than the total vaginal length in cm
4	Complete eversion of the total length of the lower genital tract

Modified Oxford Grading System to evaluate the strength of pelvic floor muscles (Power)

Table no. 8 -Scoring of Power as assessed by Modified Oxford Grading System.

Score	Power - Criteria
0	Lack of muscle response
1	Flicker of non-sustained contraction
2	Presence of low intensity, but sustained contraction
3	Moderate contraction, felt like an increase in intravaginal pressure, which compresses the fingers of the examiner with small cranial elevation of the vaginal wall
4	Satisfactory contraction, compressing the fingers of the examiner with elevation of the vaginal wall towards the pubic symphysis
5	Strong contraction, firm compression of the examiner's fingers with positive movement toward the pubic symphysis

Table no. 9 -Scoring of Endurance, Repetition & Fast Parameters.

Parameter	Criteria	Grade	Score
E (Endurance)	0 sec-2 sec	Poor	0
	3 sec-6 sec	Average	1
	7 sec-10 sec	Good	2
R (Repetition)	0-2	Poor	0
	3-6	Average	1
	7-10	Good	2
F (Fast)	0-2	Poor	0
	3-6	Average	1
	7-10	Good	2

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Table no. 10 -Statistical analysis within group A.

GROUP A	Mean \pm SD			
	BT	AT1	AT2	FU
Stage of anterior compartment prolapse	1.1 \pm 0.852	0.75 \pm 0.716	0.35 \pm 0.489	0.4 \pm 0.503
Stage of middle compartment prolapse	0.8 \pm 0.768	0.5 \pm .607	0.25 \pm 0.444	0.2 \pm 0.41
Stage of posterior compartment prolapse	1.15 \pm 0.813	0.55 \pm 0.686	0.1 \pm 0.308	0.1 \pm 0.308
Power	2.15 \pm 1.089	2.25 \pm 1.02	3.3 \pm 0.979	3.3 \pm 0.979

Endurance	0.7±0.801	0.85±0.745	1.45±0.51	1.45±0.51
Repetition	0.45±0.605	0.85±0.745	1.55±0.51	1.55±0.51
Fast	0.5±0.513	0.7±0.733	1.45±0.51	1.45±0.51
Feeling of mass per vagina	1.85±0.671	0.7±0.47	0.4±0.503	0.4±0.503
Low back ache	1.55±1.05	0.9±0.718	0.3±0.47	0.35±0.489
Frequency of micturition	1.7±0.865	0.65±0.671	0.25±0.444	0.25±0.444
Stress Urinary Incontinence	1.05±1.05	0.55±0.686	0.45±0.686	0.45±0.686
Difficulty in emptying bladder	1.3±0.979	0.55±0.686	0.45±0.605	0.45±0.605
Straining during defecation	1.1±0.852	0.5±0.513	0.2±0.41	0.2±0.41

Table no.11: Statistical analysis within group B.

GROUP B	Mean±SD			
	BT	AT1	AT2	FU
Stage of anterior compartment prolapse	1.3±0.923	0.9±0.788	0.55±0.605	0.65±0.587
Stage of middle compartment prolapse	0.9±0.852	0.65±0.671	0.45±0.605	0.5±0.688
Stage of posterior compartment prolapse	1±0.858	0.3±0.47	0.05±0.224	0.15±0.366
Power	1.75±0.716	1.85±0.813	2.8±0.768	2.8±0.768
Endurance	0.4±0.503	0.45±0.51	1.35±0.489	1.3±0.47
Repetition	0.3±0.47	0.35±0.489	1.2±0.41	1.2±0.41
Fast	0.3±0.47	0.35±0.489	1.2±0.41	1.2±0.41
Feeling of mass per vagina	1.95±0.759	1.15±0.366	0.55±0.51	0.55±0.51
Low back ache	1.35±0.988	1.1±0.852	0.5±0.513	0.5±0.513
Frequency of micturition	1.8±0.768	0.8±0.616	0.25±0.444	0.25±0.444
Stress Urinary Incontinence	0.95±1.146	0.55±0.686	0.4±0.681	0.4±0.681
Difficulty in emptying bladder	1.7±0.865	0.9±0.718	0.6±0.754	0.55±0.686
Straining during defecation	1.05±0.945	0.35±0.489	0.1±0.308	0.1±0.308

Table no.12: Statistical analysis between the groups.

	MEAN		p	Result
	GROUP A	GROUP B		
Stage of anterior compartment prolapse	0.750	0.750	0.894	NS
Stage of middle compartment prolapse	0.550	0.450	0.665	NS
Stage of posterior compartment prolapse	1.050	0.950	0.697	NS
Power	1.150	1.050	0.592	NS
Endurance	0.750	0.950	0.084	NS
Repetition	1.100	0.900	0.169	NS
Fast	0.950	0.900	0.573	NS
Feeling of mass per vagina	1.450	1.400	0.765	NS
Low back ache	1.250	0.850	0.138	NS
Frequency of micturition	1.450	1.550	0.859	NS
Stress Urinary Incontinence	0.600	0.550	0.441	NS
Difficulty in emptying bladder	0.850	1.100	0.209	NS
Straining during defecation	0.900	0.950	0.863	NS

NS – Not significant

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION ON OBSERVATIONS

Area of residence

In this study of 40 patients, 67.5% of subjects were residing in rural area and 32.5% of subjects were residing in urban area.

The reason for this could be the place where study was conducted having more of villages, rather than any relation of disease with area of residence.

Age

In this study of 40 subjects, 25% subjects were of 30-40 years of age, 32.5% subjects were of 41-50 years of age, 27.5% subjects were of 51-60 years of age and 15% subjects were of 61-70 years of age.

Prevalence of Pelvic Organ Prolapse increases from 40 years of age, perimenopausal age due to laxity of perineal supportive structures, estrogen deficiency & reduction in collagen. In the current study, less number of subjects in the age group 61-70 years of age might be because of lack of awareness and negligence towards health in advanced age group in women.

Socioeconomic status

In this study of 40 subjects, 20% subjects were of lower class, 67.5% subjects were of middle class, and 12.5% subjects were of upper class.

The maximum subjects included in the study were from middle class background, rather than any relation of socioeconomic status with the disease.

Religion

In this study of 40 subjects, 75% subjects were of Hindu religion, 17.5% subjects were of Muslim religion and 7.5% subjects were of Christian religion.

The fact may be the area where the study conducted was having predominance of Hindu religion.

Occupation

In this study of 40 subjects, 25% subjects were of employed and 75% subjects were housewives.

Physical workload at home like heavy lifting, prolonged standing and squatting for long hours for cooking, cleaning can weaken pelvic floor support over time.

Diet

In this study of 40 subjects, 25% subjects were consuming vegetarian diet and 75% subjects were consuming mixed diet.

The maximum subjects in the study were having mixed diet, rather than any direct relation of vegetarian or mixed diet with disease.

Body Mass Index (BMI)

In this study of 40 subjects, 5% subjects were of underweight BMI, 25% subjects were of normal BMI, 30% of subjects were of overweight BMI and 40% subjects were of obese BMI.

Increased intra-abdominal pressure leads to chronic stress on pelvic floor muscles, fascia, and ligaments. Adipose tissue itself may affect collagen metabolism and connective tissue strength, further weakening support structures, leading to greater risk of POP.^[8] However, being underweight doesn't completely rule out the chances of getting Pelvic Organ Prolapse, very low BMI with poor muscle and connective tissue strength may also predispose to prolapse.^[9] Therefore, BMI should be considered as a contributory but not independent determinant of POP.

Mode of previous delivery

In this study of 40 subjects, 95% subjects were having FTNVD as mode of previous delivery and 5% subjects were having LSCS as mode of previous delivery.

Each vaginal birth stretches and sometimes tears the pelvic floor muscles, fascia and connective tissue. Generally caesarean deliveries are lower risk, but do not completely eliminate it because pregnancy itself weakens pelvic tissues.

Parity

In this study of 40 subjects, 5% subjects were para 1, 37.5% subjects were para 2 and 57.5% subjects were para 3.

Higher parity especially multiple vaginal deliveries is a primary risk factor for pelvic organ prolapse. Pregnancy hormones like relaxin and progesterone increase connective tissue laxity,

making the pelvic floor more susceptible to damage. First vaginal birth causes the largest single increase in risk, but subsequent births add incremental damage.

Menstrual status

In this study of 40 subjects, 57.5% subjects were menstruating and 42.5% subjects were menopausal.

The risk of POP becomes most pronounced in postmenopausal women. Estrogen deficiency leads to atrophy of the urogenital tract, thinning of the vaginal mucosa, reduction in collagen and elastin content, and overall decline in pelvic floor muscle tone. Consequently, the majority of symptomatic POP cases are reported in this age group.^[10]

In this study, maximum subjects belonged to premenopausal stage, the reason might be small sample size.

However, pelvic organ prolapse can also manifest in premenopausal women with some factors like multiparity, traumatic vaginal deliveries, early resumption of activities in puerperium, heavy weight lifting in household activities and some aggravating factors like obesity, chronic cough and constipation etc.^[11]

Different compartment prolapses

In this study of 40 subjects, 5% subjects were having anterior compartment prolapse only, 7.5% had middle compartment prolapse only, 10% had posterior compartment prolapse only, 20% had anterior + posterior compartment prolapse, 15% had anterior + middle compartment prolapse, 12.5% had middle + posterior compartment prolapse and 30% had anterior + middle + posterior compartment prolapse.

This observation suggests that multi-compartment prolapse is more common than isolated compartment prolapse, which is consistent with previous studies.^[12]

Stage of prolapse

In this study, 8 subjects had 1st stage anterior compartment prolapse, 20 subjects had 1st stage middle compartment prolapse and 13 subjects had 1st stage posterior compartment prolapse.

In this study, 20 subjects had 2nd stage anterior compartment prolapse, 4 subjects had 2nd stage middle compartment prolapse and 15 subjects had 2nd stage posterior compartment prolapse.

In this study, no subjects had 3rd stage anterior compartment prolapse, 2 subjects had 3rd stage middle compartment prolapse and no subjects had 3rd stage posterior compartment prolapse. In this study, most of the subjects had 1st and 2nd stage prolapse of different compartments, only few had 3rd stage middle compartment prolapse and none had 3rd stage anterior and middle compartment prolapse.

Sleep disturbances

In this study of 40 subjects, 72.5% subjects were having sleep disturbances and 27.5% subjects were not having sleep disturbances.

Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) significantly impacts women's sleep quality. A cohort study revealed that 50% of women with POP reported poor sleep quality, with factors such as younger age, multiple comorbidities, and severe nocturia contributing to sleep disturbances. Additionally, depressive symptoms and prolonged sleep onset were prevalent among these women. The severity of prolapse symptoms, including urinary, bowel, and prolapse-related distress, was strongly associated with diminished sleep quality.^[13]

Low back ache

In this study of 40 subjects, 82.5% subjects were having low back ache and 17.5% subjects were not having low back ache.

Uterine or vaginal descent stretches the uterosacral and cardinal ligaments. These ligaments attach to the sacrum and pelvic fascia, their stretching or traction can refer pain to the lumbosacral area.^[14] Prolapse can alter the normal pelvic tilt and spinal alignment, increasing lumbar lordosis or causing compensatory muscle spasm. Chronic strain of paraspinal and pelvic floor muscles contributes to dull, aching back pain.^[15]

Urinary symptoms

In this study of 40 subjects, 95% subjects were having urinary symptoms and 5% subjects were not having urinary symptoms.

Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP), particularly anterior vaginal wall prolapse, is closely associated with a range of lower urinary tract symptoms. These include Stress Urinary Incontinence (SUI), urinary urgency, frequency, nocturia, and voiding dysfunction such as hesitancy and incomplete emptying.^[16]

Bowel symptoms

In this study of 40 subjects, 67.5% subjects were having bowel symptoms and 32.5% subjects were not having bowel symptoms.

Bowel symptoms in pelvic organ prolapse arise primarily due to posterior compartment defects, such as rectocele, which cause bulging of the rectal wall into the vagina and lead to obstructed defecation.^[17]

DISCUSSION ON RESULT

DISCUSSION ON EFFECT OF TREATMENT ON STAGE OF PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE

Effect of treatment on stage of Anterior Compartment Prolapse

- There is a statistically significant difference in stage of anterior compartment prolapse in group A and group B from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- When comparing the change in anterior compartment stage between Groups A and B, there were no statistically significant differences at any interval (all $p > 0.05$), indicating both groups improved similarly.

Effect of treatment on stage of Middle Compartment Prolapse

- There is statistically significant difference in stage of middle compartment prolapse in group A from baseline to follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- Group B showed no statistically significant changes in middle compartment stage across treatment intervals (all $p > 0.12$), indicating minimal improvement in this compartment.
- Comparison of middle compartment prolapse stage changes between the two groups revealed no statistically significant differences for any interval (all $p > 0.17$), suggesting that the observed effect may not differ meaningfully between the groups.

Effect of treatment on stage of Posterior Compartment Prolapse

- Stage of posterior compartment prolapse in group A dropped dramatically from baseline to at both AT2 and follow up, which were statistically significant at $p < 0.001$.
- There is statistically significant difference in stage of posterior compartment prolapse in Group B from baseline to AT1, AT2 and to follow-up at $p < 0.05$.
- Between-group comparisons in stage of posterior compartment prolapse showed no statistically significant differences at any interval, indicating similar posterior compartment responses.

Both the drugs are having *Kashaya Rasa* (astringent property), *Shoshana*, *Stambhana* and *Grahi* actions which helps to constrict the cells and brings compactness in the tissues. Both the drugs are having *Vatashamaka* property, hence contributes in reducing the pelvic organ prolapse which is a *Vata Pradhana* condition. Flavonoids, tannin, saponins present in the drugs may help in strengthening the pelvic floor as it prevents tissue damage due to its antioxidant action. *Lodhra* contains phytoestrogens and studies show presence of estrogen receptors in the vaginal mucosa and uterosacral ligaments, hence effective in pelvic organ prolapse due to estrogen deficiency.^[18] Moreover, *Tila Taila* is *Vatahara*, *Madhura Vipaka*, *Balya*, *Brimhana*, *Sthairyakara*, hence when used as *Yonipichu*, it carries these properties along with the properties of particular drugs and provides strength to the vaginal mucosa.

DISCUSSION ON EFFECT OF TREATMENT ON POWER, ENDURANCE, REPETITION AND FAST CONTRACTIONS

Effect of treatment on Power

- There is statistically significant difference in Power in group A and group B from baseline to AT2 and follow up and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$.
- No statistically significant differences between-group were observed for any power comparison.

Effect of treatment on Endurance

- There is statistically significant difference in endurance in group A at $p < 0.050$ and in group B at $p < 0.001$ from baseline to AT2 and follow up and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up.
- Comparisons of endurance improvements between Groups A and B were not statistically significant for any interval, indicating similar efficacy in both groups.

Effect of treatment on Repetition

- There is statistically significant difference in repetition in group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$ and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$
- There is statistically significant difference in repetition in group B from baseline to AT2 and follow up and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$.
- No between-group differences were statistically significant except for AT1-BT comparison, during which group A was found better.

Effect of treatment on Fast contractions

- There is statistically significant difference in fast contractions in group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$ and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$
- There is statistically significant difference in fast contractions in group B from baseline to AT2 and follow up and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$.
- Between-group differences were not statistically significant for any fast contractions parameter comparison, indicating same efficacy in both groups.

Flavonoids, tannin, saponins, gallic acid, butin and racemosic acid present in the drugs may help in strengthening the pelvic floor as it prevents tissue damage due to its antioxidant action. These components help to strengthen the connective tissues. By virtue of these chemical constituents both the drugs possess astringent property and also has estrogenic properties which results in *Yonigadheekarana* (Tightening of vaginal wall & perineum) by promoting collagen tissue growth.^[19] Addition to these, the *Tila Taila* used as a carrier for these drugs has *Vatashamaka*, *Balya*, *Sthairyakara*, *Brimhana* actions. This might have resulted in improvements in the Power, Endurance, Repetition and Fast contractions of the vagina.

DISCUSSION ON EFFECT OF TREATMENT ON SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

Effect of treatment on Feeling of Mass per Vagina

- There is statistically significant difference in the feeling of mass per vagina in group A and group B from baseline to AT1, AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$.
- There is no statistically significant difference in between-group comparison for any feeling of mass per vagina comparison, showing same efficacy in both groups.

Both the drugs have *Kashaya Rasa* (astringent property) by virtue of which there is *Shoshana* (constriction in the cells) which might reduce the feeling of mass per vagina.

Effect of treatment on Low Back Ache

- There is statistically significant difference in low back ache in group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$.
- There is statistically significant difference in Group B in low back ache from baseline to AT2 and follow up and from AT1 to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- No between-group comparisons were significant except at BT-AT1 interval, indicating early response in group A.

Here the manifestation of low back ache is a result of Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) itself, hence when the stage of prolapse decreases, simultaneously there is reduction in low back ache.

Effect of treatment on Frequency of Micturition

- There is statistically significant difference in frequency of micturition in Group A and group B from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$ and statistically significant difference from baseline to AT1 at $p < 0.05$.
- No statistically significant between-group differences were observed for any frequency of micturition comparison (all $p > 0.46$), indicating similar efficacy in both groups.

The *Stambhana*, *Vatahara* specially *Apana Vata*, *Grahi* and *Shoshana* action of the drugs might have worked in reducing the frequency of micturition.

Effect of treatment on Stress Urinary Incontinence (SUI)

- There is statistically significant difference in SUI in Group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- Group B showed no statistically significant difference in SUI at any interval (all $q < 2.685$, $p > 0.229$), however there was reduction in SUI clinically.
- Between-group differences in Stress Urinary Incontinence (SUI) change were not statistically significant for any interval.

As urethra and vagina share some common blood supply, the drug absorbed through the vaginal mucosa also reaches the urethra and its structures. *Kashaya Rasa*, *Grahi* and *Stambhana* action of the drugs may help to improve voluntary control over urethra by acting on the sphincter muscles of urethra. The *Balya*, *Brimhana* action of *Tila Taila* and other drugs also provides strength to the urethral sphincter complex.

Effect of treatment on Difficulty in Emptying Bladder

- There is statistically highly significant difference in difficulty in emptying bladder in Group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$ and statistically significant difference from baseline to AT1 at $p < 0.05$.
- There is statistically highly significant difference in difficulty in emptying bladder in Group B from baseline to AT1, AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.001$ and statistically significant difference from AT1 to follow up at $p < 0.05$.

- No statistically significant between-group differences emerged for difficulty in emptying bladder changes (all $p > 0.14$), indicating similar efficacy in both groups.

The anatomical changes in the prolapse leads to *Dushti of Apanavata* which is responsible for proper *Mutra Nishkramana* (evacuation of urine). The *Vatahara* action of the drugs and *Tila Taila* reduces this *Apanavata Dushti* and helps in easy voiding of urine. Moreover, when the stage of the prolapse reduces, the angulation of the urethra gets corrected, which promotes normal emptying of bladder.

Effect of treatment on Straining during Defecation

- There is statistically significant difference in straining during defecation in Group A from baseline to AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- There is statistically significant difference in straining during defecation in Group B from baseline to AT1, AT2 and follow up at $p < 0.05$.
- Between-group comparisons of straining during defecation were not statistically significant for any interval (all $p > 0.62$), indicating similar efficacy in both groups.

The anatomical changes in the prolapse leads to *Dushti of Apanavata* which is responsible for proper *Shakrut Nishkramana* (evacuation of feces). The *Vatahara* action of the drugs and *Tila Taila* reduces this *Apanavata Dushti* and helps in easy evacuation of bowels. Moreover, when the stage of the prolapse declines, the bulge in the posterior vaginal wall reduces, by which the need for manually pushing the bulge, effort or straining during defecation to evacuate the bowel also diminishes.

DISCUSSION ON PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION OF *LODHRA-KATUTUMBI TAILA* AND *PALASHADI TAILA*

The reference of *Lodhra-Katutumbi* can be found in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Yonivyapat Chikitsa Prakarana*, 19th verse and “*Yonidardhyakara*” effect has been mentioned. *Shoshana* action of *Kashaya Rasa* present in the drugs may also help in reduction of feeling of mass per vagina.^[19] *Grahi* and *Sthambhana* properties of drugs may oppose *Chala Guna* and helps to hold organs in position and thereby reduces the traction effect.^[19] Flavonoids, tannin, saponins present in the drugs may help in strengthening the pelvic floor as it prevents tissue damage due to its antioxidant action. These components help to strengthen the connective tissues supporting the uterus and reduces low back ache.^[19] Studies show that *Lodhra*

contains phytoestrogens^[20] which may help in hypoestrogenic state. It is mentioned that *Lodhra* does *Sankocha* of *Shleshmala Twacha* and provides strength.^[21]

The reference of control drug i.e., *Palasha*, *Udumbara*, *Tila taila* and *Madhu* is found in, *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, *Yonivyapat Chikitsa Prakarana*, 21st verse and “*Yonigadheekarana*” effect has been mentioned. *Palasha* has *vatashamaka* property due to its *Snigdha Guna* and *Ushna Veerya*. *Udumbara* has *Tridoshashamaka* property due to its *Kashaya Rasa*, *Katu Vipaka* and *Sheeta Veerya*.^[22] Both *Palasha* and *Udumbara* have astringent property due to their *Kashaya Rasa* which causes contraction in skin cell and other body tissue.^[22] Due to *Stambhana* property, helps to hold the structures in place. *Palasha* contains the tannic acid, gallic acid and butin & *Udumbara* has tannic acid, gallic acid, racemosic acid and other alkaloids by which these have astringent and oestrogenic properties results *Yonigadheekarana* (Tightening of vaginal wall & perineum) by promoting collagen tissue growth.^[22]

CONCLUSION

This randomized controlled clinical trial successfully evaluated and compared the *Yonigadheekarana* efficacy of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in the management of *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse). A central finding of this trial was the comparative analysis between the two treatment groups. Across the majority of the study's parameters - including the changes stage of anterior, middle, and posterior compartment prolapse and the improvements in Power, Endurance, Repetition and Fast-contractions, there was no statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B. This outcome strongly suggests that *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila* and *Palashadi Taila* both have similar efficacy on *Yonigadheekarana* in *Yonibhramsha*. So, here H3 is accepted that, there is no statistically significant difference in effect of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* and *Palashadi Taila Yonipichudharana* in *Yonibhramsha*.

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